

Screening rice cultivars for tolerance for waterlogging

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Tolerance for partial submergence is an essential trait for rainfed lowland rice in eastern India. We screened 22 elite cultures obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Andhra Pradesh, at the Baruipur Experimental Farm during 1989-90 wet season.

Seedlings were transplanted at 30 d in an especially created depression in the field where water depth could be maintained at 50 cm. Plot size was 5 m × 2 m. Traditional local cultivar Kumargore was the check. Varieties were assessed on yield and yield attributes (see table).

Seven IET cultures that could withstand waterlogging, in order of grain yield in g/m², were IET10016 (640), IET10102 (592), IET10009 (586), IET10003 (545), IET10084 (543), IET10109 (541), and IET10233 (527). ■

Grain yield and yield components of rice cultivars under waterlogged conditions. Calcutta, India, 1989-90.

Culture	Cross	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Spikelets/m ² (* 10 ³)	Grains/m ² (* 10 ³)	Test weight (g)	High-density grain/m ² (* 10 ³)	Yield (g/m ²)
IET9017	Selection from composites	210	23.4	19.4	17.6	4.9	331
IET10003	Jaladhi 2/Pankaj	260	25.7	23.2	31.7	11.7	545
IET10006	Pankaj/Patnai 23	280	33.4	29.4	20.1	8.4	497
IET10008	CN644/Patnai 23	280	34.9	32.0	28.7	11.5	433
IET10009	CN644/Patnai 23	250	35.2	32.3	23.5	10.0	586
IET10016	Jajati/Mahsuri	290	44.2	37.8	26.1	16.8	640
IET10027	Jaladhi 2/CN644	280	30.1	26.6	26.1	11.9	508
IET10029	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	260	28.4	23.9	22.4	7.0	444
IET10084	Bashpair/Pankaj	240	27.5	24.4	32.2	12.1	543
IET10091	CN644/Patnai 23	270	42.1	36.9	18.5	8.6	502
IET10097	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	210	23.1	16.4	23.1	4.9	445
IET10102	Jhingasail/CN644	240	50.4	46.1	25.9	18.6	592
IET10109	Jhingasail/Patnai 23	240	34.6	30.1	25.2	10.4	541
IET10115	Jhingasail/CN644	250	29.3	27.1	28.3	7.6	373
IET10173	FR43B/CNM539	180	21.8	11.4	12.0	1.5	263
IET10233	Jalamagna/IET4060	180	25.5	24.2	23.6	7.9	527
IET10234	Selection from local	270	25.4	20.6	28.5	8.7	517
IET10530	IET4060/Jalamagna	200	19.2	16.0	23.4	5.6	412
IET10536	Not known	190	31.8	23.4	29.2	9.7	419
IET10030	Velki/Mahsuri	230	19.4	13.9	23.3	5.1	298
	Sabita	300	31.7	28.6	26.9	10.7	526
	Utkaiprava	270	21.7	19.6	26.5	5.7	342
	Kumargore (local check)	290	28.2	34.6	25.2	11.9	496
	LSD (0.05)	50	7.1	7.7	0.2	2.9	182

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Screening rice varieties for salt tolerance in the greenhouse

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We screened more than 100 local and exotic rice varieties for salt tolerance in the greenhouse, using a coastal saline soil from Taishan County, Guangdong Province. Soil was clay loam with pH 8.0, 0.6% water-soluble salt content, EC 5.4 dS/m, 2.4% organic matter, 0.11 % total N, 8.8 ppm available P, 326.9 ppm available K, CEC 16.7 meq/100 g soil. Screening was carried out in two steps.

In preliminary screening, 102 varieties were tested. Dried soil (15 kg) was put into each 41- × 37- × 15-cm plastic container and soaked with deionized water 2 wk before transplanting. Three days before transplanting, urea and superphosphate were added at 50-11 mg NP/kg soil.

Rice seedlings were generated from sand culture with a modified nutrient solution. When the 5th to 6th leaf appeared, the seedlings were transplanted into the containers at 6- × 9-cm spacing, 9 seedlings/variety in a randomized block design with three replications. Deionized water was maintained 2-3 cm above the soil surface throughout growth.

At 5 wk after transplanting, plants were evaluated for salt tolerance (Table 1) and the damage index (DI) calculated for each variety. DI ranged from 50 to 100% (data not shown).

Further screening of 28 relatively salt-tolerant varieties (DI ≤ 60% in the preliminary screening) and two salt-sensitive varieties (DI = 100%) was

Table 1. Criteria for salt tolerance evaluation of rice plants.

Plant response to salinity	Plant appearance	Salt tolerance class (C _i) ^a
Normal	Normal growth.	1
Slight	Growth and tillering slightly affected. Tips of bottom leaves dried out.	2
Medium	Growth and tillering significantly inhibited. Bottom leaves withered. Tips of middle and upper leaves dried out.	3
Serious	Growth completely stops. Middle or upper leaves withered or dried out.	4
Dead	Whole plant dead or dying.	5

^a Damage index (DI) was calculated for each variety as

$$DI (\%) = \frac{Rc_i n_i}{NC_{max}} \times 100$$

where c_i is class of salt tolerance for a plant. n_i is number of plants in that class, N is total number of plants of the given variety in each replication, and C_{max} is highest class observed.